

Whether Value Education or Wither Value Education

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Abstract:- Educational institutions are mushrooming every day. In present milieu it is very much felt that education is being commercialized. The vital importance of education is to shape lives and prepare students to face life challenges with confidence and courage, but which has been forgotten. It is not having a high academic profile alone matters but pupil with values is the need of the hour in higher education today. Reflecting on the motif behind modern college going student is to excel in academia and accomplish a position. They tend to enlarge their brain with techno based information whereas in reality transformation is the key factor. In the society they rarely find an example to follow. Scanning about the present scenario educators are worried much about the decline of morality in the society. In contrast debate on whether value education or wither value education also became a dominant thought among present-day academicians. In this predicament inculcating value education is very urgent and that is the need of the hour. Value education has a significant role to play in shaping a society which is tolerant, compassionate and socially cohesive.

Keywords:- Value Education, Students, Character Formation, Community Cohesion.

I. INTRODUCTION

We live in an age of edutainment in which education is viewed as automation. Nelson Mandela asserts that education is the most powerful weapon through which you can change the world. Today education is viewed as a tool to obtain intellectual knowledge but it is also an arena of building character. Swami Vivekananda defines education as “life-building, man-making, character-making assimilation of ideas”, and not a certain “amount of information that is put into your brain and runs riot there, undigested all your life”. Ajit Mondal (2012).

In this respect, we have a clarion call to tailor the ethical and social life of students. Why do we need to reflect on such a venture? What will be the outcome of shaping students towards such values? We know that without inculcating values in the lives of students we will merely produce intellectual cocoons. Moreover we will see enormous erosion of human values and social relations. What is the remedy? How it can be tackled? It is through value education. Value education fosters meaning and purpose to life. This article analyzes the concept whether value education or wither value education in the light of its purpose and importance in shaping the moral climate of students in higher education.

II. VALUE EDUCATION

Education is necessarily a process of inculcating values to equip the learner lead a life- a kind of life that is satisfying to the individual in accordance with the cherished values and ideals of the society NCERT (2003). Oxford Dictionary defines value as something of great worth, importance, standard or principle that is valuable in life. According to Indrani (2012), Value education harmonizes the need for the student to achieve in a competitive world and the need to be compassion to his fellow beings. Value education simply means an education that brings out good qualities in a student. In the process individual tend to know life’s purpose and learn the ways of leading life in a best way possible. Moreover, it traces human values and behavioral act that everyone should adhere to make life on this planet as pacific one.

The primary objective of value education is to transform pupil into person of integrity, honesty, humility, generosity and sacrifice. It develops moral, ethical, spiritual and social values in a student. It enhances equality, perseverance and tolerance among pupil from different walk of life. Value education is a process of inculcating values and discipline in the mind of pupil. How it can be obtained? When we instill a deep and firm commitment towards values and disciplined life. In this media thronged environment educators have a great role to play in producing pupil with good morals. Thus value education shapes the individuals as well as the society as a better place to live and share. In the education sector, value education is often like talk of the town. It is being very much discussed and debated among the academic circle.

III. IMPORTANCE OF VALUE EDUCATION

Dr. Radhakrishnan has rightly said that a civilization is not built of bricks, steel and machinery, it is built with men, their quality and character. Therefore, value based education is needed to impart social and moral values, integrity, character, spirituality and many more in a person. Main idea behind value education is to cultivate essential Values in the students so that the civilization that teaches us to manage complexities can be sustained and further developed. Satyajit (2018). The very cream of education is to see genuine transformation and maturity. We witness thousands of students graduate from our universities every year. Focusing on producing students with high profile and strong moral values, every educator must pause for a moment and ask the million dollar question; whether education without value is useful or harmful? Throwing light on the present scenario one can easily scan there is continues disintegration of moral values in the society.

Globalization and commercialization of education added more fuel and signals that we are in a more dangerous zone. Will the present screen based, over informative educational process make a student really “human”? As students are more into social media and entangled with media influences, they struggle to communicate with each other in a dyadic context. Since they are much familiar with texting and online chat it became a great challenge for them. Due to the explosion of technological advancement, the world became a global village states Marshal McLuhan. Though we have become network society still social interaction have minimized in a higher level. Working among university students the author has witnessed hundreds of young minds fall prey to depression, media addiction and lives with stained ego.

We are enveloped by consumerism and individualism. Concern for others and their development is more minimized. People are becoming more selfish day by day. Where is the room for social accommodation? What are the ways of egalitarian society? Present social system and its enlargement widen the gap in social relationship. This is also prevalent among modern day youth that they are more stressed than ever. They are easily influenced by cultures around the world and forgetting our own cultural heritage and uniqueness. Accumulation of wealth, giving them more to neo-Epicureanism became new trend among the young pupil. Involvement of youth in social evils and crimes become natural nowadays. It has to be monitored regularly and need of immediate attention from the education sector if not we are running towards lasting peril some day.

In this technology era value based education is urgently needed as human life became more worsen than earlier and social progress became disoriented. (Sekhar, S.C & Emmaniel, R. 2012). There must be a crystal change in the mind and heart of both the students and parents. Equal weight age must be given in training pupil towards best possible carrier as well as character. It happens often that parents want to see their children in a highest level in the college and position but they fail to train them in proper ethical values. We must create a curriculum in which a student can anticipate holistic growth. They may learn to balance between work and family, money and relationship, individual life and social well being. Value education can play greater role in changing the lifestyle of individual students in the college.

IV. PURPOSE OF VALUE EDUCATION

A. To inculcate Virtues

Reflecting on the concept of morality Schofield(1970) perceives that the term morals implies “behavior”, and the adjectives “moral” or “immoral” suggests behavior which is accepted and unaccepted. According to him since norms or standard are established by society, there is a link between all three concepts of: value judgment, values and morals. The argument is that when a society establishes its standard of good and bad behavior, such society is making a value-judgment, because it is saying that some forms of behaviors

are more socially acceptable than others. This implies that the ability to understand and to identify with the available value judgments of a society is morality.

In this Z generation young people are prone to numerous challenges. Reflecting on the reality seen in the society that they are highly infected with diverse negative behaviors, attitudes, characters and actions. At the same time there is increase of learning centers established from the pre-primary to the College levels. Whereas the daily reports of vices in the society seem not justify the fact that education has any strong moral bearings on it products. According to Krishnamurti(1953), education should help us to discover lasting values so that we do not merely cling to formulas or repeat slogans; it should help us to break down our national and social barriers, instead of emphasizing them, for they breed antagonism between man and man. We need clarity of education that not only brings degrees but also decrees in moral blockage. Actions that are intended to bring good result for those concerned are moral actions and should be encouraged while those intended to bring about bad result are immoral and should be discouraged.

In this milieu value education will definitely make a strong moral development in the life of a student. It can be done through the study of value education. Other subjects a student tackles in the college will touch the intellectual aspect whereas value education will enable them to capture human values. Studies reveal that every society is embodied with its cultural and religious practices. These practices affect and influence the moral standard of the pupil. It is an awesome responsibility to educate our students with high morality and discipline. Our educational system must strive towards true humanity which will result in vastness of heart and compassion.

B. To offer Holistic education

Any mode of training demands a holistic approach in its content and practice, so also with education. Integrated and holistic approach towards education requires that students be developed in all the areas of life. Alongside emotional and intellectual development, one has also to invest in the moral growth and development. According to Miller (1997) holistic education is a philosophy of education based on the premise that each person finds identity, meaning, and purpose in life through connections to the community, to the natural world, and to spiritual values such as compassion and peace.

Holistic education reflects concern over an ecological consciousness; it recognizes that everything in the world exists in context. This involves a deep respect and stewardship for the integrity of the nature. Simultaneously it throws light on the innate potential of every student for intelligent and creative thinking. It is student-honoring education, because it respects the creative impulses at work within the unfolding student as much as, if not more than, the cultural imperatives that conventional schooling seeks to overlay onto the growing personality.

C. To promote Tolerance

We are living under one umbrella where people with multi cultural and religious taste. We must develop a positive attitude toward our neighbors. To have respect towards fellow students will lead towards living a caring community. Value education acknowledges and supports the notion that young people are multi-dimensional. At the same time it acknowledges the complementary and supplementary role of partnership that the college can play in the formation of tolerant society. The heart of the matter is respect and awareness between each other. This awareness and appreciation will assist in counteracting prejudice and intolerance as young people consider issues such as sectarianism and discrimination more broadly. Learning about diverse of values deepens the understanding of students and prepare them to live in harmony with neighbors of other faith. Value education promotes multicultural and anti-racist environment. Insights drawn from value education will enable students to find answer to live together with diversity.

An effective learning environment will be one where religious harmony is maintained, in which sensitivity and respect is shown for all religious traditions. The learning environment should be such that it fosters in students a positive attitude towards other people. It is a personal choice of an individual and their right to hold different beliefs. It should prepare students for living in a society of multi-religious context. Here student's field of experience is needed to be recognized. For this cause educator must incorporate principles and strategies which celebrate diversity while recognizing the varied learning styles, multiple intelligences, and abilities of the individual.

D. To prepare Responsible citizens

National Curriculum Framework (NCF 2000) stresses on inculcating of qualities such as, regularity, punctuality, cleanliness, self control, industriousness, sense of duty, desire to serve, responsibility, enterprise, and creativity, sensitivity to greater equality, fraternity democratic attitude and sense of obligation to environmental protection. Education should influence on democratic values and also empower all citizens to participate in meaningful ways in the life of the society. The building of a truly democratic society means far more than participation in the electoral role. It is beyond that which means empowering individuals to take an active part in the affairs of their community. A truly democratic society is more than the rule of the majority. It is a community in which disparate voices are heard and genuine human concerns are addressed. It is a society open to constructive change when social or cultural change is required.

Gerhard Zecha (2007) asserts that values education, however, is more basic, more essential, more central to the idea of an educated and morally responsible citizen than political education and community service learning. Value education as a subject covers topics like human values, social values, Conflict resolution, Peace and Justice. It will therefore equip pupils with the knowledge, values and skills needed to choose alternatives to self-destructive and violent behavior. The important expectation is that when they learn constructive ways to address issues which may lead to

violence, the incidence and intensity of that conflict will disappear. The best educational system always recognizes their responsibilities in the nation. Value education does exactly that.

Today among higher education institutions value education is need of the hour. We will find students from different segment of society joining the college. They are in need of proper guidance and counseling as they begin to move in a different direction altogether. We are well aware about various statutory bodies like AICTE taking much initiative in promoting balanced educational policies in the higher education institutions. Educational institutions can inculcate value education through accommodating various events in their curriculum. It must include every one irrespective of color, creed and religion. They can promote various events related to health and hygiene, segregating special holidays for community development programs. They may follow certain principles related to time management, self discipline, organizing seminars which will draw the attention of pupil to practice equality, religious harmony, national welfare and tolerance.

V. CONCLUSION

Above mentioned information is ample evidence that there is no question of withering value education in higher education institutions in our country. We are urgently in need of value education; it contains the potentiality to renovate a spoiled mind set into afresh. In order to save our youth and prolong an ethical generation there is no other option but to promote value education in our institutions. Values are the reasons and they provide a basic foundation for prestigious living in the community. A society that is consciously tied to values could be guided by the moral code of principles. Unless we promote a clear understanding of the core moral values, the values that are contained in the Constitution will result in the kind of moral bankruptcy that is associated with the abuse of human dignity. Value education is very much imitable and it offers framework for understanding the context of moral living and develop students' abilities to improve on their moral lives. Value education is concerned with the transmission and continuation of values and norms from one generation to another through the process of socialization and initiation. Let's add value to education by value education.

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